

Massage therapy is one of the oldest healing traditions. Ancient peoples such as the Egyptians, Greeks and Chinese believed that it could help with a wide range of ailments. Many health conditions can be addressed through massage therapy, including stress, anxiety, pain and insomnia. It's important to talk with your doctor before adding massage to your wellness plan, however. Some of the most common benefits of massage include improved blood flow, reduced tension and stress and increased flexibility. It can also boost your mood and reduce your heart rate.

Increased relaxation and sleep:

A study found that massage reduced cortisol, the body's "fight or flight" hormone, and increased serotonin and dopamine, neurotransmitters that help control your mood. This can make it easier to relax and drift off into a deep sleep, which in turn may help you improve your quality of life.

Decreased chronic pain:

Whether you're in pain from a sports injury or an ongoing condition like arthritis, a regular massage can be a helpful part of your healing process. Studies have shown that massage can help decrease the tightness in muscles and ease pain associated with trigger points or knots, which are areas of tense [Medical Massage Near me](#) muscle fibers that cause referred pain elsewhere. It can also be used to reduce aches and pains related to fibromyalgia, a painful condition that affects the muscles, joints and nerves. In addition, it can help desensitize areas that are painful and reduce the mind-body hypersensitivity that comes with chronic pain.

Lymphatic massage:

Lymphatic massage is a form of massage that promotes the flow of lymph, or fluid, in your body. This fluid is necessary for maintaining your immune system's function and helping rid your body of waste products. It can also be helpful in reducing inflammation, says Eric Bodner, a licensed massage therapist at the Cleveland Clinic. Preventive and maintenance therapies such as massage are becoming more widely accepted in medical settings. A growing body of research suggests that massage can be helpful for those with certain conditions, such as cancer, heart disease, stomach problems and fibromyalgia.

Find a qualified and experienced massage therapist:

When selecting a therapist, look for a person who specializes in the type of massage you want. Usually, this means that the therapist has extensive training and is certified to practice their particular area of expertise. Be sure to fill out an intake form before the first session, letting your therapist know your age, health status and any other medical issues you have. This will help the therapist to focus on your needs.

Avoid eating a heavy meal before your appointment, as this can limit the level of relaxation. Instead, eat a light meal or drink plenty of water. Before your treatment, it's also a good idea to get into the sauna for 20 minutes,

which helps warm up your body and prepare it for massage. The heat helps the therapist's hands to work more easily, and it will help you feel comfortable when the massage begins. If you are in the New York City area, Elite Healers Sports Massage is the best place to go. Book an appointment today!

Elite Healers Sports Massage is more than just a massage, it's therapy. Visit the Elite Healers Sports Massage website at <https://www.elitehealersportsmassage.com> to book an appointment or to see their hours of operation. Services include: Sports Massage Therapy, Medical Massage Therapy, Deep Tissue Massage Therapy, Swedish Massage Therapy, Thai Massage, and Chair Massage Office Events. If you are in the NYC area, schedule an appointment today!